

Evaluation of Students for Online Learning System

Khin Moe Khaine*, Khin Moe Oo**, Zin Oo Hlaing***, Kyaw Hlaing****

Abstract

Two courses for physics specialization students were uploaded on website. These are Phys-5207, Condensed Matter Physics and Phys-3203, Nuclear Physics. We used edX platform and mobile application for students. Quizzes, video files and figures were used as teaching aids. About 40 students for each course were studied. We take survey records for their online learning experiences. Their experiences, feeling, needs, expectation and suggestions were presented in this paper.

Keywords: Online learning system, open educational resources, edX platform, technology based learning

Introduction

Students like technology and applications. Nowadays, they can use smart phone. Students can access educational opportunity. So online learning is overwhelming much traditional classroom style and student's interest. Online learning can enhance the quality of learning experiences and outcomes. This technology should be used to facilitate teaching and learning environment. In addition, online learning is generally much lower in carbon intensity.

We used Moodle platform for third year honours students last year. At that time, we uploaded quizzes and assignment questions. They submitted answer for assignments as document file. This year, we used edX platform for teaching and learning. Full versions of these two courses were uploaded on online learning portal of Bago University and used open educational resources. Students use mobile applications to register and learn these courses. We take face-to-face surveys, self-administered paper and pencil surveys and online surveys for this learning system.

Results for Online Learning System

Figure. 1 Learning experiences of students

* Dr., Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

** Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Physics, Bago University

*** Dr., Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

**** Dr., Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

Figure. 2 Learning with mobile application

Figure. 3 Learning System

Figure. 4 Effect of mobile application on lesson

Figure. 5 Interesting level for other online course

Figure. 6 Quizzes and video lessons

Figure. 7 Way to mobile application

Figure. 8 Recommendation for online learning

Discussion

Learning experiences of H1 and H3 students are shown in figure 1. Most students haven't online learning experiences but some students have a little experience. They got online certificates from open educational resources. All students like mobile application and records for learning with mobile application are shown in figure 2. In figure 3, column 1 refers to face to face learning, column 2 refers to only online learning and column 3 refers to blended learning. Learning with mobile application is very useful and effective for them. Figure 4 shows effect of mobile application on lesson. Interesting level for other online course is shown in figure 5; column 1 refers to the students who don't like any online course, column 2 refers to the students who want to learn more than one course and column 3 refers to the students who want to learn all subjects as online courses. Figure 6 show the students who like quizzes and video lessons. All students like quizzes and video lessons. These are very helpful for them. To answer quizzes, they take more reading time. So they can understand the lessons. Mobile applications for two physics courses are easy way to use. The results are shown in figure 7. Most students like these online learning system and the results are shown in figure 8.

Conclusion

According to survey records, most students don't have online learning experiences. But they like online learning system with mobile application. They like prefer blended learning than only online. Some student wants to learn all subjects as online courses.

They like these system because they can learn anytime, anywhere. They also like technological based learning. To answer quizzes and assignments, they take more reading time, so they have self-study skill. They don't like essay type questions and parrot learning.

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